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DATA SYNCHRONIZATION –A SURVEY

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Abstract:

Objective- Designing a standard data synchronization protocol which is designed in such a way that it make data synchronization between IOT devices and mobile devices relatively easily compared to the existing system where the developer has to create their own logic to synchronize their applications

Design / Methodology/ Approach- To develop a web server which is the main server used, then there is a database for storing the data and finally there are the IOT devices and mobile devices that are the clients.

Findings- It requires an unique primary key for each user to identify clients. Then the use of a long-long integer value to store the current time, day, date, month and year in mille seconds. The time is called the last updated time which is the key value used to synchronize the devices

Limitations- Modification of the protocol is very easy so Security issues has to be taken into consideration.

Practical implications- This paper inspires research scholars, industrialist and academicians who are working to create their own application

Originality/Value- This will help in improving the efficiency of the developer by reducing the time for creating the application and reducing error when creating an app with data synchronization, and improving the performance of the application.

Keywords- Data synchronization, unique primary key, IOT devices

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Data synchronization is the process of establishing consistency among data from source to target data storage and vice versa and the continuous harmonization of the data over time. It is fundamental to a wide variety of applications, including file synchronization and mobile device synchronization. The data synchronization protocol mainly contains 3 part. One is a web server which is the main server used the protocol, then there is a database for storing the data and finally there are the IOT devices and mobile devices that are the clients. The data synchronization protocol helps in synchronizing the various device among each other. Nowadays the main problem faced by the developer is the lack of standard data synchronization. So they create their own data synchronization protocol to develop their Application, which works only in that specific Application. There exists no standard protocol for developing an Application. In this paper we provide a standard protocol for data synchronization, which can be used in all platforms like Web, Android, iOS, etc. Using this, protocol developers can create an Application easily without worrying about the data synchronization problem.

1.1.1 Reliable, Consistent, and Efficient Data Sync for Mobile Apps

Personal smart devices have become ubiquitous and users can now enjoy a wide variety of applications, or *apps* for short, running on them. Many such apps are data-centric often relying on cloud-based resources to store, share, and analyze the data. In addition to the user interface and the various features, the developer of such an app needs to build the underlying data management infrastructure. For example, in order to deliver a high-quality note-taking app such as Evernote, the developers have to build a data management platform that supports rich multimedia notes, queries on data and metadata, collaboration, and offline operations, while ensuring reliability and consistency in the face of failures. Moreover, a mobile app developer needs to meet the above requirements while also being efficient with the limited resources on mobile devices such as cellular bandwidth and battery power. The better the developer handles the above-mentioned issues the more likely the app will attract and retain users. With the rapid growth in the number and the variety of apps in the marketplace, there is a consequent demand from practitioners for *high-level abstractions* that

hide the complexity and simplify the various tasks of the app developer in managing data. Data-sync services have emerged as an aid to developers wherein an app can offload some of its data management to a third-party service such as Dropbox, iCloud, or Google Drive. While at first such services catered to end-users who want access to their files across multiple devices, more recently such services provide SDKs for apps to use directly through CRUD (Create, Read, Up- date, Delete) operations. Sync services are built upon decades of research on distributed and mobile data sync – from foundational work on disconnected operations, weakly-connected replicated storage, and version management, to more recent work on wide-area database replication, collaborative editing, and caching for mobile devices.

1.1.2 Sampled-Data Synchronization Control of Dynamical Networks With Stochastic Sampling

The sampled-data synchronization control problem has been addressed for a class of dynamical networks with stochastic sampling. The addressed synchronization control problem has first been transformed to the exponential mean-square stability analysis problem for a dynamic system with MPIDs as well as SBNs. By constructing a new Lyapunov functional and employing Gronwall's inequality and Jensen integral inequality, a sufficient condition has been obtained to guarantee the exponential mean-square stability of the considered dynamic system and the set of sampled-data synchronization controllers has been designed. In our future work, we will further consider the problems for randomly occurring nonlinearities and randomly occurring network topology, which would reflect more features of the complexity.

The sampling period considered here is assumed to be time-varying that switches between two different values in a random way with given probability. The addressed synchronization control problem is first formulated as an exponentially mean-square stabilization problem for a new class of dynamical networks that involve both the multiple probabilistic interval delays (MPIDs) and the sector-bounded nonlinearities (SBNs). Then, a novel Lyapunov functional is constructed to obtain sufficient conditions under which the dynamical network is exponentially mean-square stable. Both Gronwall's inequality and Jensen integral inequality are utilized to substantially simplify the derivation of the main results. Subsequently, a set of sampled-data synchronization controllers is designed in terms of the solution to certain matrix inequalities that can be solved

effectively by using available software. Finally, a numerical simulation example is employed to show the effectiveness of the proposed sampled-data synchronization control scheme.

1.1.3 Poster – iSync: A High Performance and Scalable Data Synchronization Protocol for Named Data Networking

This paper presents a high performance synchronization protocol which utilizes the IBF to synchronize published collections between nodes. The protocol uses a two-level IBF design and can reconcile a number of differences in a single comparison. We found that on average, iSync is about 66 times faster than CCNx on a range of network sizes, while it uses 18 to 48 times fewer packets. Data synchronization of multiple nodes is a fundamental operation in many Internet applications, such as cloud storage, group communication, and routing protocols. In named data networking (NDN), keeping namespaces synchronized has recently emerged as a basic service required by many NDN applications, from Dropbox - style file sharing to supporting mobile and ad-hoc vehicular communication. NDN also uses a core synchronization protocol to support a key-based trust model which requires public key exchange. The goal of a synchronization protocol is to keep a dataset (or a collection) up-to-date among distributed participants. In other words, a synchronization protocol must replicate a dataset's content among participating hosts. In NDN, a content item is represented by a namespace, so a synchronized NDN collection consists of the content names a list of namespaces. This paper describes iSync, a high performance and scalable data synchronization protocol based on IBFs. iSync uses a two-level IBF structure to support efficient data reconciliation. The first level identifies collections which are out-of-date; the second level discovers the IDs of all the items that exist in a remote collection, but are missing in the local one. This feature allows the difference reconciliation process to efficiently skip collections that have no updates.

1.1.4 Synchronization and replication in the context of mobile applications

Data replication and synchronization have been topics of research for quite some time in the area of databases and distributed databases. Through the advent of mobile computing the results of this research have to be applied to a new area of application. Before going into

details about synchronization and replication, two terms that are strongly connected to each other, a basic introduction into mobile computing has to be given. This paper is concerned with introducing the problems that arise in the context of mobile applications with respect to data synchronization and replication. Existing solutions of data replication within databases are described as well as their correspondence to data synchronization. An advanced topic in contrast to traditional mobile computing, as there is peer to peer mobile computing, is also presented as well as its specific requirements and a way of replication within such environments. There is also a discussion of the standardization efforts in the field of data synchronization mechanisms and protocols for mobile devices.

Mobile computing gives users the chance to access data that is stored in a stationary database or some other data repository at any time and any place. Data items that are located within a database, a file system or in memory as a variable within a program, can be modified by processes. If only one process at a time is trying to modify a data item, there is no need for synchronization. If more than one process at a time tries to modify a data item, it is necessary to ensure that no two processes access the data item at the same time. Accesses to the data item are put into a sequential order, which is called process synchronization.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 DATA SYNCHRONIZATION WITHOUT DRY PRINCIPLE

In the existing system application developers create their own data synchronization logic's in their application. Developer's spends most of their time solving the data synchronization problems. The developer have deal with these problem all most all the time when they are creating the application. The developer repeats these processes for every application. They are violating the Don't Repeat Yourself principle. Thus, the efficiency of the developer is reduced and thus the app performance is reduced. There is no standard protocol for data synchronization.

DISADVANTAGE

- Low efficiency

- Time consuming
- Discontinuity between devices
- Tedious work
- Low performance
- Unsatisfying D. R.Y Principle

2.2 DATA SYNCHRONIZATION WITH DRY PRINCIPLE

In the proposed system, we are here by lighting up a new protocol that enables us to synchronize our data with all other devices working in any platform. With the introduction of this so called high performances delivery assured protocol systems we will be able to reach out to all those end users who can use this system without any trouble. As data synchronization protocol, has not yet been standardised in any system there is a possibility of strategic change in the current scenario with better advancements in the linkage of various platforms.

ADVANTAGES

- High efficiency
- Lower time consumption
- Continuity between devices
- Better performance
- Satisfying D. R. Y Principle

III.SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

There are 4 modules in our data synchronization protocols.

1. User Registration
2. Creating and Updating data
3. Download data
4. API

1. User Registration

This module describes how a user register into the server with the user details. Then the server will save the details in the server data base, and create a unique ID for each user, these ID is the primary key which is used to identify the client

2. Creating and Updating data

This module describes how a client can create or add a new data into the data base. when adding a data, the server creates a special field to store a long-long integer value which contains the current time of the creation of data in seconds. These integer value is updated when a data is updated in the database. These value is used when the client request for data.

3. Download data

In this module, we describe how a user can synchronize with the server. If a client is connecting for the first time the server provide the client with entire data in the server and then the last updated value is also provided. next time when the client access the database then the client provides the last updated time which was stored in the client data base during the last synchronization is also sent with the request so the server can sent the data that was created after the last update has occurred.

4. API

The goal of this module is to implement concurrent and transaction enabled Application programming interface, to implement synchronization between different kinds of devices like IOT devices (internet of things), Android devices, java script enabled single page web apps.

3.2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture contains the complete information about the working of the data synchronization protocol. The system design mainly has a web server which is the main server which is used in our protocol. A database warehouse which is the main

data base for our project. And it also contain lots of IOT (Internet of things), mobile devices which are the clients. The server is the place where all the user connect to get various data they need. First the client register to the server and obtain a unique ID. These ID is used identify various clients. In the data synchronization process there are mainly 2 process one is creating the data and other is updating the data. When a client creates a data a unique integer is created with the current time, date, month and year. These Integer is specific for each record in the database. When user ask for data if client is synchronizing for the first time all data is sent and the last updated time is also sent along with the data. Next time when the client request for data the client also sent his last updated time along with the request. The server then gets the last updated time and then return data that is create after the last updated time of the client and sends the data and the last updated time of the last added record. When a user updates a data in the record the last updated filed in the record is changed to the current time of updating. So when other client asks for the new record the client can give the updated record. When a client delete a record the server saves the record into a special memory where the deleted records are stored when the client synchronize the server sends the data of the record that should be deleted to the client so that the client can delete that data from its memory as well.

Figure: System architecture

IV.CONCLUSION

In this paper we describe about a standard data synchronization protocol which is designed in such a way that it make data synchronization between IOT devices and mobile devices relatively easily compared to the existing system where the developer has to create their own logic to synchronize their applications. This paper mainly contains 3 part. One is a web server which is the main server used, then there is a database for storing the data and finally there are the IOT devices and mobile devices that are the clients. In these project we create a unique primary key for each user to identify clients. Then we use a long-long integer value to store the current time, day, date, month and year in mille seconds. These time is called the last updated time which is the key value used to synchronize the devices. With the implementation of this paper the developer can create an application without worrying about the data synchronization problem. These will help in improving the efficiency of the developer by reducing the time for creating the application and reducing error when creating an app with data synchronization, and improving the performance of the application.

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